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The transcriptional landscape of HER2+ subtype breast cancer in humans: CEP68.

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Breast cancer in humans is a solid tumor type with distinct subtypes historically defined by the PAM50 molecular subtype classification scheme (1-3). We utilize, in this study, whole transcriptome technologies to define the transcriptional landscape of HER2+ subtype human breast cancer (4, 5). We describe here differential expression of CEP68 in HER2+ breast cancer.

We harnessed the power of whole transcriptome technology, using only primary tumor tissues from patients with breast cancer of defined molecular subtype (4, 5) to perform differential gene expression analyses, for characterization, in molecular detail, of the tumor transcriptome of HER2+ subtype breast cancer.

Methods

We utilized microarray datasets GSE45827 (4) and GSE87049 (5) for this global differential gene expression analysis of HER2+ subtype human breast cancer in conjunction with the R-based computational differential gene expression software GEO2R. GSE45827 was generated using [HG-U133_Plus_2] Affymetrix Human Genome U133 Plus 2.0 Array technology with $n=11$ normal breast tissues (control) and $n=30$ HER2+ subtype primary tumors from humans with breast cancer; analysis was performed using GPL570. GSE87049 was generated using Affymetrix Human Gene 1.0 ST Array [transcript (gene) version] technology with $n=35$ normal breast tissues (control) $n=18$ primary breast tumors of HER2+ subtype from humans with breast cancer; analysis was performed using platform GPL6244. We used an R-based bioinformatic tool to perform whole transcriptome co-regulation studies across multiple tissues (SEEK [6]). We utilized a computational tool to measure the influence of tumor gene expression on overall survival in humans with breast cancer, in $n=1879$ patients (total), in $n=431$ basal subtype patients, in $n=596$ luminal A subtype patients, in $n=439$ luminal B subtype patients, in $n=362$ HER2+ patients, and $n=51$ normal-like subtype patients (7).

Rationale

Breast cancer in humans is a complex molecular entity that remains to be completely defined.

Results

We performed whole transcriptome profiling - subtraction analysis, also known as differential gene expression profiling - to identify and describe at the systems level the complete set of genes whose expression was most specifically activated or repressed in humans with the HER2+ subtype of human breast cancer.

1. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: HER2+ subtype

$n=11$ normal breast tissues (human)

$n=30$ primary tumors (breast; human; HER2+)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
212677_s_at	5.53E-12	9.477016	17.016347	2.2117491	CEP68	1610/29873	94.6

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal breast tissues and HER2+ breast tumors, we discovered differential expression of centrosomal protein 68, encoded by CEP68 (located at 2p14) in HER2+ breast cancer in humans (Chart 1). The expression of CEP68 changed more than 94% of the human breast and breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 29,873 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the positive fold-change indicating decreased quantity of CEP68 messenger RNA in HER2+ subtype tumors, demonstrating down-regulation of CEP68 during transformation of the breast from normal breast tissue to HER2+ breast cancer.

2. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: HER2+ subtype

$n=35$ normal breast tissues (human)

$n=18$ primary tumors (breast; human; HER2+)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
8042326	2.14E-07	5.935078	6.7676557	0.48127225	CEP68	1937/33297	94.2

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal breast tissues and HER2+ breast tumors in a second microarray dataset from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of CEP68 in HER2+ breast cancer in humans (Chart 2). The expression of CEP68 here changed more than 94% of the human breast and breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 33,297 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the positive fold-change indicating decreased quantity of CEP68 messenger RNA in HER2+ subtype tumors, demonstrating down-regulation of CEP68 during transformation of the breast from normal breast tissue to HER2+ breast cancer.

Thus, CEP68 is a gene whose differential expression defines the transcriptional landscape of the HER2+ breast cancer subtype in humans.

In breast cancer as in any solid tumor, the function of the gene identified by whole transcriptome differential gene expression cannot be assumed to be the same as in non-transformed tissues. Thus, to identify gene products likely to interact with and/or be relevant to the differentially expressed genes function in the transformed tissue, we performed whole transcriptome transcriptional co-regulation studies using SEEK, an R-based computational tool that blindly and quantitatively identifies co-expression across the genome using a clustering method rather than integration-based differential gene expression methodology (6). This second whole transcriptome technology identified KIAA0240, ZFP90, MXI1, TSHZ1, and RAB11FIP2 as the five genes across the transcriptome most closely co-regulated with CEP68 in the transformed human breast (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Transcriptional co-regulation in the transformed human breast: CEP68.

Finally, we measured the influence of CEP68 tumor gene expression on overall survival in humans with breast cancer using a computational tool (**Figure 2**) (7).

Fig. 2: Relationship between CEP68 tumor expression and overall survival in humans with breast cancer.
Caption: Overall survival in all patients (above; left), in patients with basal subtype (above; center), in patients with luminal A subtype (above; right), in patients with luminal B subtype (below; left), in patients with HER2+ subtype (below; center), and patients with normal-like subtype breast cancer (below; right) is depicted in these Kaplan-Meier plots.

Discussion

We describe here CEP68 as a component gene product of the HER2+ subtype in human breast cancer, suggesting its importance in the development or maintenance of the subtype, a product of tumor evolution in transformation of solid tissues in humans.

References

1. Parker, J.S., Mullins, M., Cheang, M.C., Leung, S., Voduc, D., Vickery, T., Davies, S., Fauron, C., He, X., Hu, Z. and Quackenbush, J.F., 2009. Supervised risk predictor of breast cancer based on intrinsic subtypes. *Journal of clinical oncology*, 27(8), p.1160.
2. Perou, C.M., Parker, J.S., Prat, A., Ellis, M.J. and Bernard, P.S., 2010. Clinical implementation of the intrinsic subtypes of breast cancer. *The lancet oncology*, 11(8), pp.718-719.
3. Prat, A., Parker, J.S., Fan, C. and Perou, C.M., 2012. PAM50 assay and the three-gene model for identifying the major and clinically relevant molecular subtypes of breast cancer. *Breast cancer research and treatment*, 135, pp.301-306.
4. Gruosso, T., Mieulet, V., Cardon, M., Bourachot, B., Kieffer, Y., Devun, F., Dubois, T., Dutreix, M., Vincent-Salomon, A., Miller, K.M. and Mehta-Grigoriou, F., 2016. Chronic oxidative stress promotes H2 AX protein degradation and enhances chemosensitivity in breast cancer patients. *EMBO molecular medicine*, 8(5), pp.527-549.
5. Romero-Cordoba, S.L., Salido-Guadarrama, I., Rebollar-Vega, R., Bautista-Piña, V., Dominguez-Reyes, C., Tenorio-Torres, A., Villegas-Carlos, F., Fernández López, J.C., Uribe-Figueroa, L., Alfaro-Ruiz, L. and Hidalgo-Miranda, A., 2021. Comprehensive omic characterization of breast cancer in Mexican-Hispanic women. *Nature communications*, 12(1), pp.1-19.
6. Zhu, Q., Wong, A.K., Krishnan, A., Aure, M.R., Tadych, A., Zhang, R., Corney, D.C., Greene, C.S., Bongo, L.A., Kristensen, V.N. and Charikar, M., 2015. Targeted exploration and analysis of large cross-platform human transcriptomic compendia. *Nature methods*, 12(3), pp.211-214.
7. Györfy, B., 2021. Survival analysis across the entire transcriptome identifies biomarkers with the highest prognostic power in breast cancer. *Computational and structural biotechnology journal*, 19, pp.4101-4109.